

Use of Phenolic Acids in the Detection, Separation and Estimation of Metals. Part IV. Colorimetric Detection of Titanium.

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Use has been made of various organic reagents in studying the colour reactions of most of the rare metals. Regarding the colour reactions of titanium mention may be made of the works of Weller (*Ber.*, 1883, 15, 2593), Levy (*Compt. rend.*, 1893, 103, 1075, 1195), Hall and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 88, 830), Fenton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1064), Muller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 1506, 1510), Lenher and Crawford (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 138). But with the exception of Weller all have used organic reagents. So far as the phenolic acids are concerned, mention may be made of Muller, and Hall and Smith.

In the present paper the action of tannic, gallic, and resorcylic acids on titanium salt solution followed by the addition of sodium acetate has been studied. It has been found that in concentrated titanium solution (1 c.c. = 0.001 gm. TiO_2), tannic acid produces an orange precipitate, whereas gallic acid produces a red-brown and resorcylic acid a faint yellow colorations. On the addition of sodium acetate to the coloured solutions the respective colours are greatly enhanced changing to deep brown and yellow. In dilute titanium solutions the colour produced with gallic acid and sodium acetate varies from reddish-brown to pale yellow; similarly with resorcylic acid and sodium acetate the colour varies from greenish-yellow to faint greenish-yellow. From the fact that tannic acid in concentrated titanium solution gives rise to precipitation and solutions containing excess of alkali or ammonium salts also become turbid by tannic acid and sodium acetate, and owing to the low sensitiveness of resorcylic acid and sodium acetate (1 part titanium in 83,000 parts), these two acids are not well-suited as reagents for the detection of titanium.

It has been observed that only gallic acid can produce maximum colour-effect in titanium solution provided that the solution is very dilute, or, if concentrated, a large excess of the reagent should be employed (for 1 c.c. solution = 0.0006 g. of Ti, at least 8-10 c.c. of 1% gallic acid are required). In extremely dilute titanium solutions, the colour by gallic acid only differs in shade with that produced by gallic acid and sodium acetate, the former being reddish-yellow and the latter greenish-yellow. The coloration produced by gallic acid (alone or along with sodium acetate) is discharged by the addition of a little dilute mineral or oxalic acid; whereas an excess of acetic acid is required for the same. Thus it is safe in every case to add sodium acetate after the addition of gallic acid to neutralise the effect of mineral acids. From the observation that, by minimising the colour-effect somewhat of the titanium solution, coloured by gallic acid and sodium acetate, with excess of 6N-acetic acid and then again adding sodium or ammonium acetate, the colour intensifies, it is concluded that sodium or ammonium acetate is essential for the maximum colour-effect, when small amount of gallic acid is used. It can be said that when the colour-forming constituents in the solution remain in maximum associated state, then and then only maximum colouration is produced. This association is helped by sodium or ammonium acetate and is retarded by acid. Similarly the maximum production of colour by an excess of gallic acid can be explained, where an excess gallic acid, like the acetate, causes the association of the colour-forming constituents; further addition of gallic acid, like the acetates, increases the colour in the titanium solution, first coloured by excess gallic acid and then faded by acetic acid.

By gallic acid, or by gallic acid and sodium acetate, an absolute amount of 0.000003 g. Ti can be detected by a pale yellow or pale greenish-yellow coloration in a volume not exceeding 4.5 c.c. In other words, the sensitiveness of the colour reaction is 1 part of Ti in 1,000,000 parts, ignoring the volume (which is generally 1 c.c.) of the reagent added. The sensitiveness in comparison with other reagents for titanium is in no way inferior. In this connection it requires to be pointed that in Muller's (*loc. cit.*) colorimetric determination of titanium by salicylic acid, the stated sensitiveness (1 part TiO_2 in 2,000,000 parts solution) cannot be attained. Strictly speaking from the colour in the body of the solution, sensitiveness stands at 1 in 100,000 parts.

The influence of the presence of many metals and salts which are likely to be present along with titanium during its course of detection has been studied. It has been found that with gallic acid, gallic acid and sodium or ammonium acetate, and with gallic acid in concentrated sulphuric acid, titanium can be detected in presence of the metals such as aluminium, beryllium, chromium, ferrous iron, cerium, thorium, yttrium, zirconium, vanadium, uranium, tungsten, molybdenum, manganese, zinc, nickel, cobalt, calcium, strontium, barium, and magnesium. With excess of gallic acid, or with gallic acid and sodium acetate, preserving the sensitiveness stated above, titanium can be detected in the presence of the metals such as aluminium, beryllium, cerium, thorium, yttrium, zirconium, zinc, manganese, calcium, strontium, barium and magnesium. In the cases of aluminium, thorium, zirconium, cerium and yttrium where gallic acid and sodium acetate produces white gelatinous precipitates, it is better to perform blank tests side by side. In presence of vanadium, before adding the reagent, sulphurous acid is added; this enables to detect 0.00003 g. of titanium in 2 c.c. without considering the volume of the reagent used. In this instance the presence of ferric iron, molybdenum and excess of tungsten and niobium interfere as they also give colour reactions with the reagent.

Titanium can be detected in presence of uranium without loss of sensitiveness as stated above. In this case dilute ammonium acetate or a little dilute acetic acid is added after the addition of sodium acetate, as the colour which uranium produces with gallic acid and sodium acetate is discharged by slight acidity (with acetic acid). In these the presence of other colour-forming elements such as molybdenum, tungsten, niobium, etc., interferes.

In detecting titanium in presence of tungsten, "perhydrol" is added before the addition of gallic acid and sodium acetate. Thereby the reddish-violet colouration changes to light violet, characteristic of titanium (evidently due to reduction of tetravalent titanium). This test enables one to detect 0.000012 g. of titanium present in 2 c.c. In this case also, in presence of other colour-forming metals such as molybdenum or iron (ferrous and ferric), the detection fails.

As a solution of alkali or ammonium molybdate with gallic acid and sodium acetate gives the same colour reaction as titanium, the detection of titanium in presence of molybdenum is not possible by this reagent. But by means of gallic acid in concentrated sulphuric acid the detection of titanium in presence of molybdenum has

been made possible and even 0·000003 g. of titanium (in 2 c.c.) can be detected. In this case too the presence of uranium, vanadium, niobium, and ferric iron interferes.

The detection of small amounts of titanium in presence of ferrous iron, which is impossible by gallic acid and sodium acetate, has also been made possible by using syrupy ammonium acetate instead of 5% sodium acetate solution. The ammonium acetate is poured into the bottom of the solution by means of a pipette and at the junction a small yellow layer due to titanium is noticeable over the violet-blue colour due to ferrous iron. In this way 0·000006 g. of titanium in presence of an excess of ferrous iron can be well detected. The presence of molybdenum, niobium and tungsten however interferes.

In presence of chromium (not excess), nickel and cobalt, the salts of which are themselves coloured, the detection of small amount of titanium is possible. In presence of excess of nickel and cobalt salts, the detection of even 0·000006 g. of titanium in 3-4 c.c. can be well done by gallic acid alone or by gallic acid and sodium acetate. It is better to carry a blank test for comparison.

The effects of the presence of alkali, pyrosulphate, phosphate and ammonium salts (fluorides, chlorides and oxalates) have been studied, with the result that the presence of alkali phosphate (irrespective of the amount) has been found to cause a diminution of sensitiveness by half and the presence of an excess of ammonium chloride causes a formation of turbidity in the test solution after a little while on the addition of the reagent. The presence of fluoride abnormally retards the formation of colour-effects; hence in its presence the detection of titanium is not at all suitable. As for the rest, no disturbing effect is observed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Titanium Solution.—The titanium solution is prepared by fusing 0·5 g. of pure TiO_2 with 6 g. of potassium bisulphate; the melt is extracted with warm 5% sulphuric acid. The solution is made up to 500 c.c. with water acidified with sulphuric acid. Hence 1 c.c. of the above solution contains 0·001 g. of TiO_2 or 0·0006 g. Ti. All the experiments are performed with this solution, only the experiments requiring details are given here. In all the experiments a fresh solution of gallic acid (saturated in cold, which is approximately 1%) is always used.

Colour reactions of titanium with gallic acid and sodium acetate.

Experi- ment.	Titanium solution (Ti).	Reagent.		Remarks.
		Gallic acid (1%)	Sodium acetate 5%.	
1.	0.000006 g. in 1 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	Greenish-yellow coloration in the body of the sol.
2.	0.000003 g. in 1 c.c.	"	"	"
3.	0.000006 g. in 1 c.c.	"	"	Formation of a pale greenish-yellow coloration at the meniscus; clearly perceptible.
4.	0.000003 g. 1 in c.c.	"	"	"
5.	0.000002 g. in 1 c.c.	"	"	No colour formation at the meniscus.
6.	0.000001 g. in 5 c.c.	"	"	Colour at the meniscus perceptible.
7.	0.000006 g. in 6 c.c.	1 c.c.	1 c.c.	Faint yellow colour in the body of the sol.; more clear, on being poured in a glazed porcelain basin.
8.	0.000003 g. in 3 c.c.	0.5 c.c. 1 c.c.	0.5 c.c. 1 c.c.	" "

From Expt. No. 8 the sensitiveness is found to be 1 part of titanium in 1,000,000 parts.

In this connection it should be noted that the presence of much free mineral acid in the titanium solution decreases the sensitiveness, for, on great dilution, the acetic acid set free in the reaction is enough to act on the colour.

Colour reaction of titanium with resorcylic acid and sodium acetate.

Expt.	Titanium solution (Ti).	Water.	Reagent.		Total volume of the Ti soln.	Remarks.
			Resor- cylic acid (sat. sol.)	Sodium acetate (5%)		
(a)	0.00006 g. in 1 c.c.	Nil	2 c.c.	1 c.c.	4 c.c.	Yellow colour having greenish shade.
(b)	"	5 c.c.	"	"	9 c.c.	Light yellow colour in the body of the soln.
(c)	"	9 c.c.	"	"	13 c.c.	Yellowish colour at the meniscus but faint in the body of the soln.
(d)	0.000006 g. in 1 c.c.	—	"	"	4 c.c.	Very faint yellow coloration at the meniscus.
(e)	0.00012 g. in 1 c.c.	—	1 c.c.	"	3 c.c.	Faint yellow colour in the body of the solution.
(f)	"	1 c.c.	"	"	4 c.c.	Yellowish coloration at the meniscus.

From (c) without considering the volume of the reagents used it is seen that 0·00006 g. of Ti in a volume of 10 c. c. can be easily detected from which the sensitiveness stands at 1 in 166,000 parts. But in (d) where 0·00006 g. of Ti is present in 1 c.c. (the same as in c) the colour is not as intense as in (c); this is due to dilution caused by the volume of the reagent (which is in this case 1-400th and in (c) is 1-130th) so to get the sensitiveness in (d) equal to (c) very small volumes of the reagent should be added, (0·5 c. c.) Using 2 c. c. of the reagent as in (e) the sensitiveness stands at 1 in 83,000.

Detection of titanium in presence of vanadium.

In mineral acid solution of vanadium, gallic acid first produces a transient pink-violet coloration (characteristic of vanadium) changing to brownish-yellow. On adding sodium acetate the solution becomes deep blue-black and of colloidal nature. But before adding gallic acid and sodium acetate, if sulphurous acid is added to the vanadium solution, a light blue solution is obtained and in presence of this coloration titanium which imparts a greenish yellow colour to the whole solution can be detected. In performing the test the volume of sulphurous acid added should be equal to the volume of the test solution and then 0·5 c.c. gallic acid and 3·4 c.c. 5% sodium acetate should be added for each 0·002 g. of vanadium. Following the above direction 1 c.c. of titanium solution of 1-20th dilution with 1 c.c. of 0·2% vanadium solution can be easily detected from the greenish-yellow colour. Thus 0·00003 g. of titanium is detectable in a volume of 2 c.c. i.e., the sensitiveness is 1 in 67,000. In this the presence of molybdenum, ferric iron and excess of niobium and tungsten interferes as, with gallic acid and sodium, acetate molybdenum, niobium, and tungsten give brown or yellow colorations and ferric iron gives deep blue-black colloidal solution. In detecting titanium in presence of vanadium it is better to perform a similar test with vanadium solution only, side by side for comparison.

Detection of titanium in presence of tungsten.

Gallic acid, or gallic acid and sodium acetate produces a yellow coloration with a solution of sodium tungstate. To this by adding dilute sulphuric acid the colour becomes dark brown (this may serve

as a sensitive test for tungsten) whereas with titanium solution gallic acid and sodium acetate produce a reddish-brown to yellow coloration according to the amount of titanium present. As both titanium and tungsten produce coloration almost of the same nature, it is difficult to identify titanium in presence of tungsten; with large amounts of titanium however, its presence can be detected as by the addition of gallic acid and excess of sodium acetate, a brown coloration will be produced due to the presence of titanium, whereas it is only yellow with a greenish shade in the case of tungsten. When small amounts of titanium are present, the reagent cannot distinguish titanium; but by the behaviour of dilute sulphuric acid on the colored solution, tungsten can be found out but not titanium, as with sulphuric acid the yellow solution becomes brown in the case of tungsten and colourless in the case of titanium.

To detect the presence of small amounts of titanium in tungsten, to the feebly acidic solution at first "perhydrol" is added and then gallic acid and excess of sodium acetate which gives a reddish-violet to light violet coloration with titanium according to its amount and no coloration at all with tungsten. After 2-3 minutes, the appearance of the violet coloration becomes more prominent. The optimum conditions for performing the test are as follows:

1. The solution should not contain much free mineral acid (in that case a large excess of sodium acetate is required, which diminishes the sensitiveness of the reaction).
2. Excess of "perhydrol" should be added (for 2 c.c. test solution at least 2 c.c. are added).
3. Gallic acid added should be small (0.5 c.c. for 2 c.c. test solution).
4. Sodium acetate should be added in excess, till the light yellow colour of the solution is discharged.
5. Tungsten should not be present in large excess, as in that case a large excess of sodium acetate is required to make the solution (which is of pale yellow colour) colourless and thus the sensitiveness is much diminished.

Small amounts of vanadium (of the order 0.0004 g.) and niobium, on being treated as above behave like tungsten. Consequently titanium can also be detected in their presence. Molybdenum and iron on being thus treated give brown and blue-black colorations respectively and thus interfere with the detection of titanium.

Detection of titanium in presence of molybdenum.

Studying the action of gallic acid in concentrated sulphuric acid on aqueous or dilute acidic solutions of all colour-forming metals such as uranium, titanium, vanadium, niobium, iron (ferrous and ferric), molybdenum and tungsten, it has been found that with the exception of tungsten and ferrous iron, all produce more or less brown colorations. If the reagent is added carefully such that it forms two distinct layers, molybdenum produces a yellow layer at the zone of contact and titanium a violetish-brown layer which becomes more visible after 2-3 minutes. Whereas others also at first form coloured layers, which readily distribute throughout the solution; the colour due to vanadium and ferric iron distributes only in the upper layer and that due to uranium in the lower layer only. It has been found that in their presence the detection of titanium in presence of molybdenum is not possible.

When both titanium and molybdenum are present in a solution, the brown layer due to titanium rests on the yellow layer due to molybdenum. After standing, the brown layer is seen between two yellow layers, thus the colour due to molybdenum slowly distributes in the upper layer. By this test titanium can also be detected in presence of tungsten and ferrous iron. Gallic acid in concentrated sulphuric acid with tungsten produces a white precipitate, turning to yellowish white after sometime. The presence of titanium in tungsten is detected by the formation of a brown layer below the yellowish-white precipitate probably of tungstic oxide, with a slight colorless gap between the two. The reagent produces practically no coloration with ferrous iron. Further in this connection the action of the reagent on a mixture of tungsten and molybdenum solution has been studied with the result that a yellow layer is obtained below the first formed white precipitate due to tungsten. The precipitate in this case gradually becomes green instead of yellowish and this is evidently due to molybdenum. This test seems to be characteristic of molybdenum, and consequently the presence of molybdenum in tungsten can be easily detected. When a solution contains titanium, tungsten and molybdenum, on the addition of the reagent, at first the brown layer due to titanium over the yellow layer due to molybdenum is noticed and after a longer time, a white turbidity due to tungsten appears, which on standing increases in bulk and becomes green.

In the colour reaction of titanium with gallic acid and sodium acetate, it has been found that the colour produced is proportional to the amount of titanium present in a solution and hence its colorimetric determination seems possible. The work is in progress.

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